

BOILING POINTS OF NORMAL PARAFFINS

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A formula $T_b = \sqrt{\frac{An+B}{1+Cn^2}}$ has been worked out from which the boiling point of any normal paraffin up to pentatriacontane ($C_{35}H_{72}$) can be calculated to a fair degree of accuracy under different pressures

It has long been observed that there is a definite relationship between the physical properties and chemical constitution of compounds. Boiling point constitutes one of the important physical properties of substances, and efforts have been made from time to time to correlate the boiling point with molecular structure. Hermann Kopp was the first to investigate the boiling points of organic compounds and the relation to their chemical constitution (*Annalen*, 1842, 41, 86, 169).

At first, Kopp was of the opinion that in all homologous series the average difference in boiling points between two successive members was 19° . As illustration, he quoted the alcohols, acids, some esters and nitriles, whilst later Schmidt and Fieberg (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 498) added the series of fatty ketones. Kopp's later researches (*Annalen*, 1844, 50, 71; 1845, 55, 166; 1847, 64, 212; 1848, 67, 356; 1850, 76, 180) showed that in many cases the difference was greater than 19° , and he modified his views accordingly. Church (*Chem. News*, 1859, 1, 205) agreed with Kopp that the difference for CH_2 was constant throughout any given series, but he pointed out that the value was different in different classes of compounds.

Schorlemmer (*Annalen*, 1872, 161, 281; 1878, 170, 150) pointed out that in the fatty hydrocarbons and their derivatives the value for CH_2 fell off continuously on ascending the series, and Zwicke and Franchimont (*ibid.*, 1872, 164, 333) noted the same behaviour with fatty acids and their esters.

This decreasing effect of additional CH_2 is found in most of the organic families, and it is now generally accepted as the normal behaviour of homologues.

Attempts were started to furnish a quantitative expression to the relationship between the boiling point and the molecular weight or the number of carbon atoms of the members of homologous series. Goldstein (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 689, 851; 1882, 15, 724) proposed the following formula for the boiling point (t_b) of a normal paraffin in degrees centigrade :

$$t_b = 380 \cdot \frac{n-1}{n} + (n-1) 19 - 340.9^*$$

* Throughout this paper—

“ n ” stands for the number of carbon atoms in the compound.

“ M ” stands for the molecular weight of the compound.

“ T_b ” stands for the boiling point in degrees absolute of a normal paraffin having n carbon atoms, under 760 mm pressure.

This formula is approximately applicable from ethane ($n = 2$) to dodecane ($n = 12$), but not beyond. It is also not applicable to methane where it gives an absurd value -340.9° , a temperature below absolute zero.

Hinrichs (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1891, 8, 229) put forth two formulae :

(i) $k_1 (\log n - q_1)$ for higher members

(ii) $k_1 (\log n - q_1) + k_2 (q_2 - \log n)^2$ for lower members

where k_1 , k_2 , q_1 , and q_2 are constants.

Walker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 193, 725) gave the formula

$$T_n = aM^b, \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ are constants.}$$

This formula represents the boiling point for only about ten consecutive members of any series. In original paper it has been shown to be true from heptane to hexadecane.

Young (*Phil. Mag.*, 1905, 9, 1) pointed out that the difference in boiling point between two successive homologues might be regarded as a function of the absolute temperature. Thus,

$$T_{n+1} - T_n = \frac{144.86}{T_n^{0.6146} \sqrt{r_n}}$$

Nekrasov (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, A141, 378; 1930, A145, 216; *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 61, 2027) gave two formulae :

$$(i) \quad T_n = K \frac{M - \Sigma}{\sqrt{\Sigma}}$$

$$(ii) \quad T_n = \frac{KM^2}{\Sigma}$$

where K is a constant, and Σ is the sum of certain empirical values allotted to each type of atom, linkage, etc. The formula (ii) is applicable only to non-polar compounds.

Burnop (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 826, 1614) stated that the quantity $M \log_{10} T + 8\sqrt{M}$ was additive.

The value of this function for any compound is denoted by (b) . From the value of (b) , calculated for various homologous series, certain empirical atomic and structural values have been obtained.

Kinney (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 3032; 1939, 61, 3236) advocates the formula

$$T_n = 230.14(N)^{\frac{1}{3}} - 543$$

" N " is termed boiling point number, and its value for any compound is the sum of certain empirical values allotted to each type of atom, linkage, etc.

More recently, Egloff, Sherman and Dull (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, 44, 730) have proposed the following equation

$$T_n = 745.42 \log (n + 4.4) - 416.31.$$

It gives good results from ethane to nonadecane.

In the present paper attempts have been made to derive a formula from which the boiling point of any normal paraffin up to pentatriacontane ($C_{35}H_{72}$) under different pressures can be calculated to a fair degree of accuracy. The formula is

$$T_n = \sqrt{\frac{An + B}{1 + Cn^2}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where A , B and C are constants. It may be put as

$$\sqrt{\frac{A(n + K)}{1 + Cn^2}}$$

where $K = B/A = \text{constant}$.

For boiling points under 760 mm. pressure

$$T_n = \sqrt{\frac{21720n - 11820}{1 + 0.00283n^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{21720(n - 0.545)}{1 + 0.00283n^2}}$$

The observed values, calculated values and the errors are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Carbon atoms	Paraffins	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.	Carbon atoms.	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.
1	Methane	111.5	99.5	+ 12*	11	Undecane	468.9	468.6	+0.3
2	Ethane	184.7	177.8	+ 6.9*	12	Dodecane	489.3	489	+0.3
3	Propane	230.9	230.7	+ 0.2	13	Tridecane	507	508	-1
4	Butane	272.6	273.3	- 0.7	14	Tetradecane	525.5	526.2	-0.7
5	Pentane	309.1	310	- 0.9	15	Pentadecane	543.5	543.3	+0.2
6	Hexane	342	342.5	- 0.5	16	Hexadecane	560.5	559.5	+1
7	Heptane	371.5	371.9	- 0.4	17	Heptadecane	576	574.8	+1.2
8	Octane	398.8	398.9	- 0.1	18	Octadecane	590	589.2	+0.8
9	Nonane	423.8	423.8	0	19	Nonadecane	603	603.1	-0.1
10	Decane	447	446.9	+ 0.1					

Another formula,

$$T_n = \sqrt{T_{n-1}^2 + 20800 + 200n - 25n^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

represents the relation between two consecutive members of the normal paraffin series. Thus, the boiling point of the next higher member of the homologous series can be calculated from the boiling point of the preceding member and *vice versa*.

The values calculated from this formula and their deviation from the observed values are given in the following table.

* It is a well known fact that the lowest members of a series depart from the regular behaviour exhibited by the higher members amongst themselves.

TABLE II

Carbon atoms.	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.	Carbon atoms.	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.
1	Methane	111.5	...	...	11	Undecane	468.9	468.9	0
2	Ethane	184.7	183.2	+1.5	12	Dodecane	489.3	489.3	0
3	Propane	230.9	235.2	-4.3	13	Tridecane	507	508.5	-1.5
4	Butane	272.6	274.9	-0.3	14	Tetradecane	525.5	525.1	+0.4
5	Pentane	309.1	309.1	0	15	Pentadecane	543.5	542.6	+0.9
6	Hexane	342	341.5	+0.5	16	Hexadecane	560.5	559.6	+0.9
7	Heptane	371.5	371.4	+0.1	17	Heptadecane	576	575.3	+0.7
8	Octane	398.8	398.9	-0.1	18	Octadecane	590	590	0
9	Nonane	423.8	423.8	0	19	Nonadecane	603	603	0
10	Decane	447	447.1	-0.1					

Boiling point of a series of compounds is a magnitude arbitrarily selected in so far as the pressure under which the compound boils is itself quite arbitrarily chosen equal to 760 mm. Hence, if any boiling point formula is correct, it is expected that simply by changing the constants the formula will give the boiling points under different pressures. Walker (*loc. cit.*) showed that his formula was applicable (though only to about 10 members) under different pressures. So is also the case with formula (1) suggested in this paper. For boiling points under 15 mm. pressure it becomes

$$\sqrt{\frac{12400(n-0.55)}{1+0.0001485n^2}}$$

It is applicable from dodecane ($C_{12}H_{26}$) to pentatriacontane ($C_{35}H_{72}$) (boiling points of paraffins lower than $C_{12}H_{26}$, and those of above $C_{35}H_{72}$, under 15 mm. pressure being not available). No formula suggested by any previous worker is applicable beyond $C_{20}H_{42}$, and thus the distinct advantage of this formula over others is that the boiling point at lower pressures of any normal paraffin from $C_{12}H_{26}$ to $C_{35}H_{72}$ can be calculated.

The following table gives the comparative statement of the values calculated from this formula and those given in literature.

TABLE III

Carbon atoms.	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.	Carbon atoms.	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.
12	Dodecane	371	373	-2	24	Tetracosane	516	517.6	-1.6
13	Tridecane	387	388.1	-1.1	25	Pentacosane	...	526.7	...
14	Tetradecane	402.5	402.6	-0.1	26	Hexacosane	...	535.5	...
15	Pentadecane	417	416.6	+0.4	27	Heptacosane	543	543.9	-0.9
16	Hexadecane	430.5	429.8	+0.7	28	Octacosane	...	552.2	...
17	Heptadecane	...	442.5	...	29	Nonacosane	...	560	...
18	Octadecane	454.5	454.4	+0.1	30	Triacontane	...	567.6	...
19	Nonadecane	466	466	0	31	Hentriacontane	575	574.8	+0.2
20	Eicosane	478	477.2	+0.8	32	Dotriacontane	583	581.9	+1.1
21	Heneicosane	488	487.9	+0.1	33	Tritriacontane	...	588.5	...
22	Docosane	497	498.1	-1.1	34	Tetraatriacontane	...	595	...
23	Tricosane	507	508.1	-1.1	35	Pentatriacontane	604	601.5	+2.5

TABLE IV

For B.P. under 30 mm. pressure :

$$\sqrt{\frac{13270(n-0.55)}{1+0.0001084n^2}}$$

Carbon atoms	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.
11	Hendecane	369.5	370	-0.5
12	Dodecane	386.8	386.8	0
13	Tridecane	403	402.8	+0.2
14	Tetradecane	418.5	418.1	+0.4
15	Pentadecane	433	432.7	+0.3
16	Hexadecane	447	446.6	+0.4
17	Heptadecane	460.5	460.1	+0.4
18	Octadecane	473	473	0
19	Nonadecane	485	485.4	-0.4

TABLE V

For B.P. under 50 mm. pressure :

$$\sqrt{\frac{14100(n-0.55)}{1+0.000136n^2}}$$

Carbon atoms	Paraffins.	Obsd. value.	Calc. value.	Error.
10	Decane	363	363.7	-0.7
11	Hendecane	...	382	...
12	Dodecane	...	399.2	...
13	Tridecane	415.5	415.5	0
14	Tetradecane	431	431.2	-0.2
15	Pentadecane	446	446	0
16	Hexadecane	460.5	460.3	+0.2
17	Heptadecane	474.5	473.9	+0.6
18	Octadecane	487.5	487	+0.5
19	Nonadecane	499.5	499.5	0

TABLE VI

For B.P. under 100 mm. pressure :

$$\sqrt{\frac{15670(n-0.55)}{1+0.0001724n^2}}$$

Carbon atoms.	Paraffin.	Observed value.	Calculated value.	Error.
11	Hendecane	400	400.5	-0.5
12	Dodecane	418.5	418.4	+0.1
13	Tridecane	435.5	435.4	+0.1
14	Tetradecane	451.5	451.5	0
15	Pentadecane	467	466.9	+0.1
16	Hexadecane	481.5	481.5	0
17	Heptadecane	496	495.5	+0.5
18	Octadecane	509	509	0
19	Nonadecane	521	521.7	-0.7

From the above tables it will be noticed that the agreement between the calculated and the observed values is fairly good.

The boiling points of halides, amines, ethers and various other derivatives are being investigated.

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